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D6.2 Cross-national Social Sciences survey best practice guidelines

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Abbreviations and Acronyms

ABS	Australian Bureau of Statistics
ADA	Australian Data Archive
AES	Australian Election Study
API	Application Programming Interface
AUSSA	Australian Survey of Social Attitudes
AUSSI-ESS	Australian Social Survey International – European Social Survey
CDIF	Cross-Domain Interoperability Framework
CODATA	Committee on Data of the International Science Council
DDI	Data Documentation Initiative
DDI-CDI	Data Documentation Initiative - Cross-Domain Interoperability
DRUM	Digital Representation of Units of Measure
ELSST	European Language Social Science Thesaurus
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
ESS	European Social Survey
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
FIP	FAIR Implementation Profile
ICPSR	Inter-University Consortium for Political and Social Research
IUSSP	International Union for the Scientific Study of Population
ISSP	International Social Survey Program
SDMX	Statistical Data and Metadata Exchange
SDR	Survey Data Recycling
SSSOM	Simple Standard for Sharing Ontology Mappings

Executive summary

The Social Surveys Work Package (WP06) of the WorldFAIR project is focussed on the improvement of FAIR practices in the management of harmonised content in cross-national social surveys. The first report from the Work Package (Deliverable 6.1) provided an overview of the practices of comparative (cross-national) social surveys, through case studies of: (1) the European Social Survey (ESS) and (2) a satellite study, the Australian Social Survey International – European Social Survey (AUSSI-ESS). The focus of this Deliverable 6.2 is oriented towards progress on three recommendations (Rs) from that first report - the use of the DDI Lifecycle and variable cascade (R6.1 and R6.2), and requirements for formal registries of variables and reusable content (R6.5). To achieve this, this paper explores the development of recommended practices for the management and processing of cross-national survey data for the establishment of harmonised social science datasets.

In this deliverable, we outline a proposed workflow for the processing of data harmonisation of social surveys, that takes account of the practical steps required to bring diverse content together in a machine-actionable way, and that could best take advantage of external registered, persistent content. This workflow considers the core steps involved in the harmonisation process, key issues that occur in the processing of data during this process, and potential resolutions of these issues. These resolutions are all oriented towards improving FAIR practices in the harmonisation process - through the use of reusable, accessible metadata structures that can both improve processing consistency for current projects, and be applied to future harmonisation projects.

The key conclusions are two-fold. Firstly, there is a key need for the application of standardised workflows to enable consistent interaction with registry content held across multiple data repositories. The proposed workflow detailed in this report is a first effort at such a workflow model. Secondly, there is a need for consistent pre-processing of data and metadata within repositories to reduce error handling in the harmonisation process. The final section of the report provides an initial set of processing rules that could be used in such circumstances. The final third phase of this Work Package will then focus on testing this workflow and rules on new waves of data coming from the AUSSI and ESS projects.

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1. Introduction

The Social Surveys work package of the WorldFAIR project is focussed on the improvement of FAIR practices in the management of harmonised content in cross-national social surveys. The first report from the Work Package (Deliverable 6.1)¹ provided an overview of the practices of comparative (cross-national) social surveys, through case studies of: (1) the European Social Survey (ESS) and (2) a satellite study, the Australian Social Survey International – European Social Survey (AUSSI-ESS). That report considered the reasons for comparative social surveys such as the ESS and related initiatives, and the foundations of the European Social Survey and its satellite studies. It then continues to consider the current data management and harmonisation practices of study partners in the ESS, including business practices, technical infrastructure and related data management at the Australian Data Archive (ADA) and Sikt, the work package partners.

Six recommendations resulted from that initial assessment of current practice:

- Recommendation 6.1: The ADA should move to the use of the DDI Lifecycle Version 3.3.
- Recommendation 6.2: The ADA should adopt the use of the DDI Variable Cascade for the management of their time series and longitudinal content.
- Recommendation 6.3: The ADA and Sikt should undertake a pilot to test the use of common libraries and scripts in the processing of ESS and AUSSI-ESS content.
- Recommendation 6.4: A public repository of template scripts should be made available for reuse in processing other cross-national datasets.
- Recommendation 6.5: ADA and Sikt should establish formal registries of variables and other reusable metadata and content, and expose current internal content from these registries for reuse through API services.
- Recommendation 6.6: Where possible, common content such as harmonised variables and code mappings should be persistently identified and made available through such registries to enable standardised and reusable harmonisation practices.

The focus of this Deliverable 6.2 is oriented towards progress on three of these recommendations - the use of the DDI Lifecycle and variable cascade (R6.1 and R6.2), and requirements for formal registries of variables and reusable content (R6.5).

To achieve this, this paper explores the development of recommended practices for the management and processing of cross-national survey data for the establishment of harmonised social science datasets. In this deliverable, we outline a proposed workflow for the processing of data harmonisation of social surveys, that takes account of the practical steps required to bring diverse content together in a machine-actionable way, and that could best take advantage of externally registered, persistent content. Our emphasis here is on the data management processes involved, rather than the requirements of establishing the conceptual equivalence of two data

¹ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7599652>

sources. The reason for this is that there is a well-established literature focussing on the conceptual and methodological requirements of data harmonisation, but very little on the specific processing steps required to build a harmonised data file.

1.1 Structure of this report

The report begins with an overview of the core areas of activity in the harmonisation process. This includes a discussion of three core requirements for the management of data in the harmonisation process - data structures, processes and workflows - and applicable technical standards, particularly the use of the DDI variable cascade as a foundation for harmonisation.

The core of the report focuses on the workflows of data harmonisation - specific processing steps that are applied to link two or more variables, and key data and metadata requirements that could be established to support these workflows. Through illustrations from current harmonisation projects, we examine key issues that arise in the harmonisation process, and possible approaches for resolving these issues. The emphasis of these approaches is oriented towards establishing persistent, reusable reference content based on external registries that could be reused both within the AUSSI-ESS context and more broadly. A short final section to the report then provides a set of recommended pre-processing actions that could be applied to data prior to harmonisation that would reduce the amount of processing required to map variables.

The paper then concludes with a discussion of next steps for the Work Package: using and testing the recommended practices, in line with the remaining recommendations from D6.1 (standards adoption, templates and libraries). In that work package, pilot methods applying the recommended practices will be used to pilot processing of the forthcoming waves of ESS and AUSSI-ESS.

2. Process of data harmonisation

The purpose of cross-national data harmonisation is to support the study of social and political processes across societies and jurisdictions. To enable these analyses, researchers require a data set which includes comparable content across concepts of interest. These include both substantive topics of study, such as political orientation² or trust in governments³, as well as comparable demographic and economic information⁴ for enabling comparative analysis of life situation and social context. The term data harmonisation has therefore been adopted as a:

“generic term for procedures used predominantly in official statistics that aim at achieving, or at least improving, the comparability of different survey measures collected” (Granda and Blasczyk, 2016, p.1).

Broadly speaking, there are two core methods for the design of cross-national data harmonisation⁵ studies:

- Ex-ante harmonisation - where the conduct of the data collection study is intended to be comparable in advance;
- Ex-post harmonisation - where the data collection occurs with no specific intention of comparability in mind.

This can be distinguished from the stage in the conduct of the study at which the data harmonisation occurs. Here, we can again identify two approaches:

- Input harmonisation - where the study collects the same information from all participants through a predesigned and coordinated questionnaire;
- Output harmonisation - where the information is collected separately by each country, and then harmonised after the fact.

From these two classifications, Wolf et al. (2017) derived a basic typology of three broad approaches (Figure 1):

- Input translation and adaptation: use of the same survey questionnaire in all contexts, along with the same survey methodology (sampling, data collection procedures, etc.);

² Dalton (2016/2021) - <https://doi.org/10.1093/acrefore/9780190228637.013.72>

³ OECD (2021) - <https://www.oecd.org/governance/trust-in-government/>

⁴ These are variously termed “background variables”, “demographics”, or “sociodemographics” in comparative studies.

⁵ As Wolf et al. (2017) note, these methods also apply to harmonisation of data within a country or language, or within a time series.

- Ex-ante output harmonisation: collection of data using the same survey questions, but with pre-designed re-coding to accommodate specific country requirements;
- Ex-post output harmonisation: import of “existing data and build an integrated database with variables following a common definition” (Wolf et al., 2017).

Figure 1. Harmonisation approaches (Source: Wolf et al. 2017, Figure 33.2).

2.1 Models of data input and output harmonisation

These generic approaches to harmonisation have been relatively broadly adopted across the social survey community. Within the sector, initiatives such as the Cross-Cultural Survey Guidelines⁶ have sought to provide guidance to comparative survey researchers on the broad set of issues that should be addressed in the harmonisation process. For example, Granda and Blasczyk (2016) propose the following five step guidelines:

1. Decide what type of harmonisation strategy to employ, taking into account that many harmonisation efforts will require some combination of strategies.

⁶ <https://ccsg.isr.umich.edu/>

2. When deciding which variables to harmonise, create an initial plan and define clear objectives about what you want to achieve. The plan should include making all data conversions reversible.
3. Focus on both the variable and survey levels in the harmonisation process.
4. Develop criteria for measuring the quality of the harmonisation process. This includes testing it with users knowledgeable about the characteristics of the underlying surveys, the meaning of source variables, and the transformation of source variables into target variables.
5. Provide the widest range possible of data and documentation products about the entire harmonisation process.

The challenge of such procedures is that while these processes are beneficial for guiding human-led harmonisation processes, it does not enable machine-to-machine interoperability of the harmonisation process. There is a need to implement more fine-grained approaches to articulate each of the above steps in greater detail.

It is for this reason that this paper is focussing on a relatively small subset of the above procedures - with a particular emphasis on the variable harmonisation level in the process (as in step 3 above). Many of the stages articulated above focus on elements that are determined earlier in the research process such as questionnaire design and survey methodology. In the ESS, for example, there are well-established and documented procedures for each of these stages already in place⁷. While improvements to these procedures can be proposed, it is at the level of data processing that this paper is intended to focus.

At the level of data (and specifically variable) management, there is much less guidance readily available. Dubrow and Tomescu-Dubrow (2015) note that there is much less standardisation in practices, with no clear methodological tradition. As such, we draw here on approaches within the cross-national survey domain and other traditions to propose a set of issues and recommended practices for the processing and management of harmonised survey data.

2.1.1. Harmonisation of populations

A related issue for data harmonisation is the question of whether the variables are representative of the same population⁸. Where the population responding differs, statistical differences between the

⁷ <https://www.europeansocialsurvey.org/methodology/>

⁸ This is more accurately specified as within the same “universe” in DDI and SDMX terms. In DDI-CDI, a universe is “Specialized unit type, with the specialization based upon characteristics other than time and geography.” For a group of people, additional characteristics for people might “...be used in defining membership in the Universe, such as age, sex, residence, income, veteran status, criminal convictions”. See https://ddi-alliance.bitbucket.io/DDI-CDI/DDI-CDI_v1.0-rc1/field-level-documentation/DDICDILibrary/Classes/Conceptual/Universe.html?highlight=universe

groups can be the result of differences in the group represented, rather than differences in their experience. This problem arises in several circumstances:

- Where the population being sampled in the survey differs in significant ways (e.g. where one country samples all residents, but another samples only citizens);
- Where the respondents to the survey are asked questions that result in different eligibility to complete the question of interest (e.g. if you are studying trust in government, and non-citizens are not asked the question about their level of trust in the government).

In the AUSSI-ESS use case used in WP6, this is not an issue as the same instrument was used and the same population was sampled (a nationally representative survey of residents of aged 18 and over). This is achievable as AUSSI-ESS was developed using an ex-ante design to be comparable with ESS. This issue does arise however in ex-post harmonisation, where the data collection is not initially intended to be harmonised (i.e. an ex-post design). Three different WorldFAIR work packages have noted a similar issue in their work⁹, suggesting that is an area for development in future WorldFAIR activity.

2.2 Data harmonisation workflows

Given the limited literature on fine-grained workflows for harmonisation, there have been some recent initiatives that seek to address these concerns. The most prominent of these has been the efforts associated with the Survey Data Recycling project¹⁰. Members of this group have been working over the past ten years to examine and compare outputs from cross-national projects such as the European Social Survey and International Social Survey Program (ISSP), including detailed analysis of both documentation and variable-level metadata and content. One recent output of this work has been a proposed workflow model for post-hoc survey data harmonisation (Kołczyńska, 2022). In the first iteration of this work, Kołczyńska (2022) proposes a three stage model of survey data harmonisation:

1. Selection of source variables for harmonisation;
2. Mapping source values to target values;
3. Recording characteristics of source items and surveys.

A more detailed specification of Kołczyńska's process is detailed in Figure 2, below. The workflow below seeks to articulate the business process being undertaken, along with the machine operations required to achieve that business process.

⁹ These are Work Package 6 (Social Surveys), Work Package 7 (Population Health), and Work Package 8 (Urban Health)

¹⁰ <https://wp.asc.ohio-state.edu/dataharmonization/>

Figure 2(b) retroharmonize() R package

Figure 2. Harmonisation workflows (Source: Kołczyńska, 2022; Antal, 2022).

The particular value of Kołczyńska’s work, however, has come with the extension of her efforts in the implementation of this workflow in a series of R functions as part of the now published “retroharmonize” R package (Antal, 2022). The refinement of the workflow has led to a more detailed articulation of the workflow steps required, and the relevant R functions, to achieve these steps in the workflow. The revised ‘retroharmonize’ workflow and machine operations are also presented as a six-step process:

1. Importing;
2. Harmonisation of concepts;
3. Harmonisation of variable names;
4. Harmonisation of variable numerical codes and labels;
5. Consistent types;
6. Reproducibility and documentation.

It is this six-step workflow that will be used as the organising model for the recommended practices throughout this report, as this workflow addresses the level of granularity required to process content at the level required for the type of machine interoperability that we are seeking.

In addition, there is notably a dedicated effort to seek to align these workflows with both DDI and Statistical Data and Metadata Exchange (SDMX) standards, making explicit recognition of the need for standards for metadata exchange, as well as the potential use of registries for the purposes of accessing existing reference classifications and standards¹¹. At the time of writing, the DDI integration has not been completed¹² but for the purpose of these recommended practices, it is possible to outline suggested approaches.

2.3 Data structures in survey datasets

The process of metadata harmonisation in survey datasets is greatly assisted by a standard set of content in the data files, although the terminology used does vary between software packages. Four common elements of a variable are relevant here:

- The **variable** (including the variable **name** and **label**);
- The **representation** (text, numeric, categories);
- **Properties** of the representations:
 - For categorical representations, the **categories** and **codes**
 - For numerical representations, the **units of measurement**
 - For text representations, the text **properties**;
- The **encoding** of the values in the dataset (e.g. character encoding, data types, etc.)

These elements are represented in standard formats in most statistical analysis packages used in the social sciences including SPSS, Stata and R. A standard representation of a categorical measure is presented in Figure 3, demonstrating the relationship between these elements in reference to a single variable, “marital status”.

¹¹ Antal, 2022 - <https://retroharmonize.dataobservatory.eu/articles/codelist.html>

¹² See commentary in the retroharmonize documentation - <https://retroharmonize.dataobservatory.eu/articles/concept.html>

Figure 3. Survey data variable metadata - categorical variables (Source: DDI Alliance).

2.4 Standardisation

While the metadata of datasets varies between systems, researchers and archives in the social sciences have long-established approaches for managing such content. The two most prominent of these are the Data Documentation Initiative (DDI)¹³ in research data archives, and the Statistical Data and Metadata Exchange (SDMX)¹⁴ in the official statistics community.

2.4.1 The Data Documentation Initiative (DDI) and the Variable Cascade

Exchange of research data between archives across countries was established over sixty years ago in the social sciences, through archives such as the Inter-University Consortium for Political and Social Research (ICPSR)¹⁵. The use of data dictionaries for variable and dataset documentation extends back to the 1970s. With the advent of the World Wide Web in the 1990s, there was further interest in the development of machine-to-machine information exchange, leading to the establishment of the Data Documentation Initiative (DDI) in the late 1990s as a means of standardising the exchange of metadata and related information about tabular data in interoperable formats. A key outcome of the DDI Codebook format was to enable the transfer of data and metadata between major

¹³ <https://ddialliance.org/>

¹⁴ <https://sdmx.org/>

¹⁵ <https://www.icpsr.umich.edu/web/pages/>

statistical software packages, which had generally adopted internal data formats which could not be used in other packages.

DDI now has three current product lines - Codebook¹⁶, Lifecycle¹⁷ and the forthcoming Cross-Domain Interoperability (CDI), currently in public review¹⁸. The previous deliverable in this WP identified where and how the different forms of DDI were used in the partner organisations ADA (DDI-Codebook) and Sikt (DDI-Lifecycle). For this deliverable, we focus on the potential uses of DDI-Lifecycle and DDI-CDI for further enhancing machine interoperability.

Along with a specific metadata schema for representing the content of social surveys (variables, codes, categories, etc.), the DDI model also includes structures for representing relationships between different parts of the content of one or more datasets. At the core of this is the DDI variable cascade, which provides a structure for enabling both the description of individual variables, and the relationship between variables across datasets and collections (such as between datasets from two or more different countries). The core structure of the variable cascade has three levels, reflected in Figure 4:

1. The **conceptual variable**: which provides a common variable specification without a specific representation. For the example, this is the concept of marital status;
2. The **represented variable**: provides a common variable specification with its specific representation (e.g. codes and categories, valid numeric ranges, acceptable inputs);
3. The **instance variable** (or just **variable** in DDI Lifecycle): provides a specification of an actual variable in use in a completed dataset.

The interaction of these three levels of the cascade allows a data manager or researcher to specify the relationship between instance variables in use in specific datasets (such as country files in AUSSI and ESS) and the characteristics used across the datasets that enable comparability between specific instances. So, for example, if a researcher sought to specify a comparable variable for “marital status”, they could specify details at each level of the variable cascade.

¹⁶ <https://ddialliance.org/Specification/DDI-Codebook/>

¹⁷ <https://ddialliance.org/Specification/DDI-Lifecycle/3.3/>

¹⁸ <https://ddialliance.org/Specification/ddi-cdi>

Figure 4. The DDI variable cascade (Source: DDI Alliance).

Two examples of this are illustrated in Table 1, below: an illustration of two similar but distinct concepts of “registered marital status” and “civil status”. Depending on the research question of interest, a researcher may wish to use either or both of these concepts. The use of the variable cascade enables the comparison of the different conceptualisations, and similarly a comparison of the differences in representations that already exist (noting that researchers will often adopt their own representation).

Table 1. Illustrating the variable cascade.

Cascade level	Registered marital status	Civil status
Conceptual variable Definition without representation	“a person’s formal registered marital status” (Australian Bureau of Statistics, 2021)	“the civil (or marital) status of an individual, i.e. the legal, conjugal status of an individual in relation to the marriage laws or customs of the country” (SDMX, 2013)
Represented variable Addition of representation	1 - Never married 2 - Widowed 3 - Divorced 4 - Separated 5 - Married @ - Not applicable (URL:	S - Single person M - Married person W - Widowed person D - Divorced person L - Legally separated person P - Person in registered partnership Q - Person whose registered

	https://www.abs.gov.au/census/guide-census-data/census-dictionary/2021/variables-topic/household-and-families/registered-marital-status-mstp)	partnership ended with the death of the partner E - Person whose registered partnership was legally dissolved (URL: https://registry.sdmx.org/sdmx/v2/structure/codelist/SDMX/CL_CIVIL_STATUS/1.0 , URN: urn:sdmx:org.sdmx.infomodel.codelist.Codelist=SDMX:CL_CIVIL_STATUS(1.0))
Instance variable Use within a specific dataset (e.g. AUSSI or ESS) ¹⁹	https://ess-search.nsd.no/en/variable/32558258-72b1-479b-8cca-49c9d569408d	https://ess-search.nsd.no/en/variable/a67d4544-ed93-4598-a381-4587399f96fe

The variable cascade forms the basis of the Colectica registry system²⁰, in use in both ADA and Sikt. This provides a foundation for establishing commonly-used variables and other metadata across the two partners, and more generally within cross-national studies.

2.4.2 Statistical Data and Metadata Exchange (SDMX)

The Statistical Data and Metadata Exchange (SDMX) standard has its origins in the official statistics community. This community also has a strong interest in metadata and data exchange for the purpose of producing cross-national statistics such as in the United Nations and European statistical systems. SDMX was established to enable the exchange of aggregate data files, such as national accounts or labour force statistics, rather than individual unit record data of the type found in social surveys. Given the focus on tables of aggregates rather than individual records, some of the structures required for the management of individual data files are not available in SDMX. That said, there are some foundations of the technical infrastructure in SDMX which are of interest for the establishment of variable registries in ADA, Sikt and the broader DDI community²¹.

A key foundation for SDMX is the set of core classifications and standards which form the basis for the content of data exchange between partners. Established under international agreements such as UN statutes, the SDMX Statistical Standards²² outline standardised terminology, definitions and code and category lists for agreed sets of statistical concepts used within its community. These

¹⁹ Note that these ESS variables are not exact instances of the represented variables that are in the European Social Survey - but are used for purposes of illustration

²⁰ <https://docs.colectica.com/repository/functionality/repository/repository-overview/>

²¹ Recent work by CODATA and the International Union for the Scientific Study of Population explores this in detail for the establishment of FAIR vocabularies in demography (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7818157>)

²² https://sdmx.org/?page_id=3215

standards are often then aligned with national standards and classifications (such as the Australian Bureau of Statistics classifications in Australia²³) to allow streamlined, computable transformation of aggregate data between source and target variables.

The other core element of the SDMX model is in the technical infrastructure established for the coordination of SDMX classifications and terminology. The most prominent aspect of this is the SDMX Global Registry²⁴, which provides a global infrastructure for referencing the terminology and metadata content agreed to in the SDMX classifications. Screenshots of the SDMX Global Registry, presented in Figure 5 below, illustrate some of the core elements available in the Registry. It is, however, the API access to the registry that provides the key functionality for machine interoperability. The capacity to access and coordinate around globally-agreed standards for codes, measures and terminology using machine-actionable methods provides the capacity to feed into data processing pipelines in a way not available in the smaller DDI-based registries²⁵.

Figure 5(a). The SMDX Global Registry codelist search interface.

²³ <https://www.abs.gov.au/statistics/standards>

²⁴ <https://registry.sdmx.org/overview.html>

²⁵ Establishing a means for federation of the various DDI-based registries was a recommendation of the CODATA-IUSSP report (Section 10.3).

registry.sdmx.org/items/codelist.html

SDMX Global Registry

Viewing: Civil (or Marital) Status [1.0]

Position	Id	Name	Description
1	S	Single person	This code includes persons who have never been married or in registere...
2	M	Married person	This code covers both persons living in a same-sex marriage as well as i...
3	W	Widowed person	This code includes persons whose marriage ended with the death of the ...
4	D	Divorced person	This code includes persons whose marriage ended with a divorce proced...
5	L	Legally separated person	This code includes persons who are separated: they are still married, but...
6	P	Person in registered partnership	This code covers both persons living in an opposite-sex registered partn...
7	Q	Person whose registered partnership ended with the death of the partner	This code includes persons whose registered partnership ended with the...
8	E	Person whose registered partnership was legally dissolved	This code includes persons whose registered partnership ended with a le...

Showing 1 to 8 of 8 entries

Selected Item Details

Name

Description

Close

Figure 5(b). The SMDX Global Registry codelist display.

2.5 Learning from other domains

The combination of the DDI variable cascade and SDMX model of registries provides a good starting point for the establishment of a framework for standards for use in social surveys. To facilitate more cross-domain support, it is useful to consider where more generalised approaches have been developed that reflect problems or use cases similar to those faced in the social sciences. Two areas in particular are immediately identifiable in this space: mapping of terminologies, and use of units of measurement.

2.5.1 Mapping of terminologies

The challenge of mapping between terminologies used within or between domains is one that has been of interest to ontology developers for some time. To this end, there has been a recent effort to establish a cross-domain approach for such mappings, resulting in the recently published Simple

Standard for Sharing Ontology Mappings (SSSOM)²⁶. The aim of SSSOM is to provide the means for the representation of mapping between source and target concepts using semantic web approaches. As detailed in the SSSOM specification, there are three core elements to an SSSOM mapping:

- The mapping itself; that is, a triple <subject, predicate, object> that reflects a correspondence of a subject entity (for example, a class in an ontology) to an object entity, (for example, an identifier in some database), via a semantic mapping predicate, such as `skos:exactMatch`.
- A mapping justification, which is the process or activity that led us to consider the mapping to be correct or reasonable. Typical examples include: labels match exactly; two classes are logically equivalent; a domain expert determined that two terms reflect the same real world concept.
- Provenance metadata, including information about author and `mapping_tool`.

Figure 6, below, illustrates the set of available properties for describing the mapping between two terms.

2.5.2 Units of measurement

While DDI and SDMX have mechanisms for supporting units within variable and question descriptions, the population of this content is often missing or poorly defined. In part, this is due to ambiguity inherent in some social science measurement; for example, in the use of semantic scales for the measurement of attitudes and values. Nonetheless, it is possible to specify at least some of the properties associated with such measures. For example, attitude scales will often use integers to reflect points on the response scale, or questions on costs will use standardised measures such as “US Dollars”. Embedding these units more effectively in variable information should assist in improving the process of harmonisation.

There has been a major effort by CODATA over the past five years to support such standardisation. The Digital Representation of Units of Measure (DRUM) task group has been working to establish standardised means for interacting with machine-actionable unit of measure definitions²⁷. The problem they seek to address, similar to that considered here, is as follows:

“Researchers across fields often assume that their colleagues understand details without specifying them, and are therefore remiss when documenting units.

²⁶ <https://mapping-commons.github.io/sssom/>

²⁷ <https://codata.org/initiatives/task-groups/drum/>

Sometimes they leave them out entirely, provide ones that have multiple definitions or use units of convenience that have never been formally recognized.”²⁸

While the standardisation of the representation of units and their interoperability is not yet complete, there are efforts to incorporate such interoperability within the WorldFAIR Cross-Domain Interoperability Framework (CDIF)²⁹ that may be applicable to the social survey domain and therefore could be trialled for use. CODATA’s DRUM task group has identified a significant number of unit registries that could be leveraged in this area.

Mapping
author_id
author_label
comment
confidence
creator_id
creator_label
curation_rule
curation_rule_text
issue_tracker_item
license
mapping_cardinality
mapping_date
mapping_justification
mapping_provider
mapping_source
mapping_tool
mapping_tool_version
match_string
object_category
object_id
object_label
object_match_field
object_preprocessing
object_source
object_source_version
object_type
other
predicate_id
predicate_label
predicate_modifier
publication_date
reviewer_id
reviewer_label
see_also
semantic_similarity_measure
semantic_similarity_score
subject_category
subject_id
subject_label
subject_match_field
subject_preprocessing
subject_source
subject_source_version
subject_type

Figure 6. Mapping fields available in the SSSOM standard.

²⁸ <https://doi.org/10.1038/d41586-022-01233-w>

²⁹ <https://worldfair-project.eu/cross-domain-interoperability-framework/>

3. The harmonisation process and core challenges

Having established the foundations of a harmonisation process and some core standards for the management of harmonisation content, it is now possible to establish a basic workflow for the data harmonisation process. Here we consider the basic procedures required in each stage, looking at the means of conducting each step along with potential challenges at each stage. We adopt the retroharmonize/SDR model (from Figure 2) and the six steps detailed there as our potential process. As the retroharmonize developers note, the practicalities of data harmonisation “means that questionnaire items are mapped into variables with a consistent numerical coding, descriptive metadata (variable and value labels) and a consistent handling of missing and special values”³⁰. Each of these is handled in a different stage in the SDR workflow.

Using the SDR process, we present an overview of the experiences in harmonising two Australian national datasets, the Australian Survey of Social Attitudes and the Australian Election Study, to illustrate key issues identified at each stage. In the final section, we then outline procedures for addressing these challenges, which will form the foundation for future testing in Deliverable 6.3 of this work package.

3.1 Importing data

To import data, it would be preferable to directly access the data file through an API login, in a reproducible and persistent way. For ADA data files, this is directly achievable through the ADA Dataverse portal, through the use of the Dataverse API³¹, using a standard GET command:

```
GET
http://$SERVER/api/access/datafile/:persistentId?persistentId=doi:10.5072/FK2/J8SJZB
```

There are also various client libraries that have been developed that provide wrappers for the Dataverse API, including for R and Python (the languages used at ADA and Sikt).

For access to ESS data files, it is necessary to follow a manual login and download process³². Files are accessible using the ESS Data Portal hosted by Sikt, and all files have a DOI to persistently reference the dataset being accessed. Notably, however, the variables in the ESS download system have been harmonised already using a model consistent with that presented here. As such, we will focus on the management of unharmonised data (such as AUSSI-ESS) as the basis for the analysis here.

³⁰ https://retroharmonize.dataobservatory.eu/articles/survey_harmonization.html

³¹ Dataverse Data Access API documentation: <https://guides.dataverse.org/en/latest/api/dataaccess.html>

³² This is due to a new portal implementation currently in development.

3.2 Harmonisation of concepts

Concept harmonisation refers to the process whereby a researcher will seek to “find information related to sufficiently similar concepts that can be harmonised to be successfully joined into a single variable, and eventually a table of similar variables must be joined” (Antal, 2022).

Wolf et al. (2017) identify a common workflow for the establishment of harmonised concepts - leading from the establishment of the theoretical concept to be observed, through to the creation of the questionnaire item(s) and eventually the data capture and coding of content into relevant variables in a tabular dataset. This workflow is presented in Figure 7.

Figure 7. From concept to question to variable (Source: Wolf et al., 2017).

It is important to note that in ex-post harmonisation, this workflow cannot be applied as the content was not intended to be harmonised in advance. Many cross-national surveys (and indeed surveys generally) make use of existing questions in their development, rather than establish entirely new measures. This may include the adoption of existing standardised measures where the process above has already been completed³³, or adaptation of such questions and/or variables³⁴. This reuse of common content means that the alignment of questions and variables with similar content is less diverse than might be expected.

³³ The Kessler psychological distress scale is one such commonly used instrument - https://link.springer.com/referenceworkentry/10.1007/978-94-007-0753-5_3663

³⁴ Common forms of adaptation are included in the Cross-Cultural Survey Guidelines chapter on adaptation: https://ccsg.isr.umich.edu/chapters/adaptation/#Common_forms_of_adaptation

The core challenge then at this point becomes one of locating suitable variables for harmonisation. For the researcher, this involves a review of the core variable metadata, but also the underlying conceptual content of the source variables to be used, along with the question items that populated the variables. Much of this content is accessible, often through the information available in a data dictionary (including the variable, representation and format properties outlined earlier), along with related documentation.

For the most part, the creation of a concept harmonisation requires a review and then comparison of available variables relevant to the concept domain of interest. This will include three broad stages, with additional sub-steps:

1. Determining the concept of interest;
2. Establishing the target variable(s);
3. Establishing the source variable(s).

3.2.1 Determining the concept of interest

Determining which concepts need to be harmonised is essentially driven by the researcher's question of interest. It is essentially a theoretical exercise, seeking to align the measures to be included with the available (or collectable) data. For the data manager or data processor, the concept is generally determined in advance by the project lead or business manager and as such will be taken as pre-determined in the harmonisation process here.

However, the researcher may be interested in being able to locate relevant concepts in use in a dataset. In this circumstance, including the documentation of concepts in variable metadata, such as the concept associated with the conceptual variable (e.g. marital status) or with the categories used in a response domain or category list (such as "married", "divorced", "separated") may also be documented.

It is in these circumstances that the use of an external classification or vocabulary may be of interest. In the case of the IUSSP-CODATA project, consideration was given to the use of FAIR vocabulary services for the standardisation of demographic terminology that was in use in the domain, and the capacity to support persistent reference to the definition of the concept in use³⁵. Here a terminology service such as a vocabulary or ontology server could provide the persistence of the concept terminology. The concept can then be mapped into a DDI variable using an external reference.

³⁵ See for example the use of the terms "fecundity" and "fertility" in that working paper.

3.2.2 Establishing target variables

Having determined the concept of interest, it is then possible to establish a characterisation of the target variable - the form of the variable that is intended in the completed dataset. This essentially has three elements, consistent with the DDI variable cascade, linking the underlying **concept** to the **conceptual variable** reflecting the representation of the categories or acceptable values that the response to the question input might take, and then the assignment of **codes** to the categories. The three elements are:

- 1) Establishing a target **conceptual variable** which represents the **concept** of interest (a DDI Conceptual Variable) and the categories or acceptable values of the responses to questions;
- 2) Establishing the target **represented variable**, which connects the categories to the set of acceptable code representations (codes/categories/ranges) that the target variable will take, using a recommended **Representation**³⁶;
- 3) Determining the data encoding and format of the target variable.

This is a second potential opportunity for the use of a variable registry. Particularly in the case of standardised measures (such as background demographic measures, or statistical classifications) there is a significant interest in mapping diverse source content into the international standard. Establishment of a variable registry (including either or both conceptual and/or represented variables) would allow researchers and data managers to import predefined variable structures as target variables.

3.2.3 Establishing source variables

The third stage of the concept mapping involves the identification of suitable source variables that can be mapped into the target variable (i.e. to create a target **instance variable**). This stage requires interaction with existing instance variables to determine their potential alignment with the target represented variable.

1. Finding relevant source variables - information search through variable information in online catalogues and registries;
2. Accessing the metadata related to these variables - returning the information in a human- and machine-processable format for review and evaluation;
3. Evaluating the metadata (and possibly data) associated with the variables for inclusion, adaptation or exclusion.

³⁶ <https://ddi-lifecycle-documentation.readthedocs.io/en/latest/TechnicalGuide/Representations.html>

The selection of source variables is currently an essentially semi-manual or entirely manual process. This is achieved by searching online variable banks (such as the UK Data Archive’s Discovery service) or reviewing data dictionaries from existing datasets (such as files imported in “Step 1 - Import” above). For the most part, researchers will then extract relevant information they need to compare and contrast available variables, but this can be a time-consuming and inaccurate process.

It is possible to leverage API services and scripting to assist in this process. For existing processed datasets, the metadata has generally been generated in a machine-actionable format, such as DDI, JSON, or internal statistical package formats such as the Tidyverse formatting for R software. An example taken from the ‘retroharmonize’ R library is included below in Figure 8, which reads an example data file (a Eurobarometer survey downloaded from the GESIS data archive), extracts metadata from the internal file format, and then searches the variable labels for text containing the term “trust” and “european_parliament”.

```
# Load the retroharmonize package
library("retroharmonize")

# Generate metadata associated with the file - from GESIS Eurobarometer)
metadata_create (
  survey_list = read_rds (
    system.file("examples", "ZA7576.rds",
               package = "retroharmonize")
  )
)

# Search the generated metadata
subset_example_metadata <- example_metadata %>%
  filter ( grepl("^unique_identifier_in|trust|country_code", .data$var_label_orig) )
%>%
  filter ( grepl("^unique_identifier_in|european_parliament|country_code",
                .data$var_label_orig)) %>%
  filter ( var_name_orig != "unqid")
```

Figure 8. Reading and finding variables in retroharmonize.

The process of evaluating metadata, however, is still however semi-manual as the researcher must review all of the associated content (variables, codes, representations and associated questions and methodology) to determine the comparability of the content.

There have been some efforts to seek to streamline the variable selection process. Efforts at variable harmonisation in epidemiology and health sciences, such as the HarmonyData project discussed below, have used semantic similarity methods to seek to automate the matching process. This may not however be the most viable method available in the social sciences, given that

concepts are used both at the level of the variable, and in the constituent categories. For example, the variable “sex” may refer to gender-related characteristics, or to the activity of sexual intercourse, depending on the context. Any algorithmic method will need to use both the variable label and additional reference information (such as categorical responses, but also question details) to determine similarity.

While this multidimensional assessment of similarity may be possible, an initial review of current tools did not identify many possible methods for this. One possible line of future development may come from the HarmonyData project³⁷. This project has been using natural language processing through a Transformer Neural Network architecture to establish semantic similarity of questionnaire items in the mental health domain, including some question items often used in the social sciences. Initial testing of this tool for the purposes of source variable identification was completed but the degree of inaccuracy in the results (particularly the number of false negatives returned) suggest that there is additional development required before automated methods of variable selection would be viable.

3.3 Harmonisation of variable names

The process of variable name harmonisation is relatively straightforward to achieve. All DDI variables have an associated name and label, and can be given an identifier that can be used to persistently identify the variable. As such, the available metadata to establish consistent names, identifiers and labels is available in the metadata within the DDI variable cascade. An example of this is the “Marital Status” variable established within the Australian Survey of Social Attitudes - the Australian component of the International Social Survey Program - which has a conceptual variable and associated represented and instance variables for all waves of the data from 2003 to the most recent 2022 study. A sample snippet of the underlying DDI Lifecycle XML for the conceptual variable is included in Figure 9 below. This content is all managed within the Colectica repository system.

Notably here, the following content is all referenceable, enabling establishment of clear, persistent target variables for harmonisation:

- URN - “urn:ddi:au.ausiriss:beb3da7b-a6e8-4959-ad94-c70406224f19:1”
- ConceptualVariableName - “AU_MARITAL”
- Label - “Legal partnership/marital status”

```
<Fragment xmlns:r="ddi:reusable:3_3" xmlns="ddi:instance:3_3">  
  <ConceptualVariable isUniversallyUnique="true">
```

³⁷ <https://harmonydata.ac.uk/>

```

versionDate="2023-07-19T23:53:57.566346Z" xmlns="ddi:conceptualcomponent:3_3">
  <r:URN>urn:ddi:au.ausiriss:beb3da7b-a6e8-4959-ad94-c70406224f19:1</r:URN>
  <r:Agency>au.ausiriss</r:Agency>
  <r:ID>beb3da7b-a6e8-4959-ad94-c70406224f19</r:ID>
  <r:Version>1</r:Version>
  <r:UserAttributePair>
    <r:AttributeKey>extension:CustomField</r:AttributeKey>

<r:AttributeValue>{"Title":{"en":"Notes"},"Description":{},"ValueType":0,"HasValue":true,"RelationshipTargetType":"00000000-0000-0000-0000-000000000000","StringValue":"issp 2011","MultilingualStringValue":{},"BooleanValue":false,"HasDefinedType":false,"DisplayLabel":"Notes"}</r:AttributeValue>
  </r:UserAttributePair>
  <r:UserAttributePair>
    <r:AttributeKey>extension:CustomField</r:AttributeKey>
    <r:AttributeValue>{"Title":{"en":"ELSST
Concept"},"Description":{},"ValueType":0,"HasValue":true,"RelationshipTargetType":"000
00000-0000-0000-0000-000000000000","StringValue":"https://elsst.cessda.eu/id/3/edc187c
7-a676-4190-98e3-077a1a333ad1","MultilingualStringValue":{},"BooleanValue":false,"HasD
efinedType":false,"DisplayLabel":"ELSST Concept"}</r:AttributeValue>
  </r:UserAttributePair>
  <r:UserAttributePair>
    <r:AttributeKey>extension:CustomField</r:AttributeKey>

<r:AttributeValue>{"Title":{"en":"Comparability"},"Description":{},"ValueType":0,"HasV
alue":true,"RelationshipTargetType":"00000000-0000-0000-0000-000000000000","StringValu
e":"Variable matched, codes not yet
matched","MultilingualStringValue":{},"BooleanValue":false,"HasDefinedType":false,"Dis
playLabel":"Comparability"}</r:AttributeValue>
  </r:UserAttributePair>
  <r:VersionResponsibility>Steven.McEachern@email.org</r:VersionResponsibility>
  <r:VersionRationale>
    <r:RationaleDescription>
      <r:String xml:lang="en">AuSSA concordance update</r:String>
    </r:RationaleDescription>
  </r:VersionRationale>
  <ConceptualVariableName>
    <r:String xml:lang="en">AU_MARITAL</r:String>
  </ConceptualVariableName>
  <r:Label>
    <r:Content xml:lang="en">Legal partnership/marital status</r:Content>
  </r:Label>
</ConceptualVariable>
</Fragment>

```

Figure 9. Conceptual variable representation in DDI Lifecycle.

With a clear target variable in mind, it is a straightforward process to map source variables into the target variable. This is readily achieved through the creation of a source and target variable matrix of the form presented in Table 2.

Table 2. A sample source-target variable matrix.

TargetVariable	SourceAustralia	SourceNorway	SourceOther
maritalstatus	Var01	Demo27	Col10
civilstatus	Var02	Demo28	Col54
....			

The final stage of variable mapping then simply requires the creation of new variable information (e.g. a new column header, or a new variable name) using common “renaming” code. For example, renaming of an existing source instance variable into a target variable could be achieved in both SPSS and R (Figure 10). Code to execute these transformations can be generated programmatically from the variable mapping matrix above.

```
# SPSS code
rename variables (marstat2018 = marstat)
# R Tidyverse code
mydat_tibble <- mydat_tibble %>%
  rename(marstat2018 = marstat)
```

Figure 10. Transformation of variables.

The retroharmonize approach however adds an additional beneficial feature - the retention of the source variable original metadata in a reusable structure. The use of a long format data structure enables the retention of the original source variable labels (and value labels) along with the target variable labels. The extended matrix required by retroharmonize is reflected in Table 3.

Table 3. Extension of the source-target variable matrix for use in retroharmonize.

Target_Variab le_Name	Target_Variab le_Label	Original_Vari able_Name_A ustralia	Original_Vari able_Label_A ustralia	Original_Valu e_Code_Nor way	...
maritalstatus	Legal marital Status	Var01	Legal marital status	Demo27	...
civilstatus	Civic marital status	Var02	Partnering arrangement	Demo28	...
....

This additional detail adds some complexity and load to the documentation required, but enables the recovery of the original variable metadata. The transformation of the variable names requires retention of both the source and target names and labels, but allows for the comparison across different states in the transformation process (see Table 6, below, for an example from the retroharmonize package that generates a crosswalk table matrix mapping original and target variable names³⁸). This transformation could likely also be extended to include external references

³⁸ <https://retroharmonize.dataobservatory.eu/articles/crosswalk.html>

to conceptual and represented variable registries (for target variables) and instance variable registries (for source variable metadata).

```
# Create crosswalk table "ct"

ct %>%
  mutate ( var_name_target = case_when (
    var_name_orig == "rowid" ~ .data$var_name_orig,
    var_name_orig == "isocntry" ~ "geo",
    TRUE ~ "trust_ep"
  )) %>%
  distinct ( across(all_of(c("filename", "var_name_orig", "var_name_target"))))
```

Figure 11. *retroharmonize* code to generate a crosswalk table - encoding the source-target variable matrix.

3.4 Harmonisation of variable numerical codes and labels

The variable mapping from source to target requires a corresponding mapping of the codes and categories used in each of the source variables to the target variable. This again can be achieved through a code matrix - essentially an alignment of the individual codes and categories used in the original and target variables. The challenge in these crosswalks is in the relatively large size of the matrices that can result from these mappings. Such mappings can also highlight differences in the use of codes, categories and data management standards between constituent source datasets. We provide an illustration of the different challenges in this process through an example from the Australian Survey of Social Attitudes - the mapping of respondent's reported religious affiliations across the waves of the AuSSA survey from 2003 onwards³⁹ - in Figure 12.

³⁹ For space reasons, the representation is cropped after the 2017 wave, but continues through until the current wave of data collection in 2022.

Item Name	V346	V434	V620	v433	h30	E35	E27	D28	I30	AU_RELIG	AU_RELIG	AU_RELIG
Don't know					-7							
Illegible or impossible value					-6							
Multiple responses					-5							
No partner					-4							
SKIP - NO RELIGION			-2									
Skipped					-2							
MISSING	-2	-2	-1	-1	-1							
No religion					1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
Catholic	1	1	1	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2
Anglican/Church of England	2	2	2	2	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4
Protestant					3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3
Uniting Church/Methodist	3	3	3	3	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
Other Protestant												
PRESBYTERIAN AND REFORMED	4	4	4	4								
Orthodox	5	5	5	5	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	7
ORTHODOX (E.G. GREEK OR												

Figure 12. Code and category comparison over time - Australian Survey of Social Attitudes.

The code and category mapping presented in Figure 11, which is generated using the Colectica automated data concordance tools, illustrates the various mapping challenges that need to be overcome in the processing of a single variable. Within this single Religious Affiliation variable, we see four core alignment challenges that need to be addressed (Table 4).

Table 4. Harmonisation challenges in mapping codes and categories.

Harmonisation problem	Religion Example	Source code	Source category	Target code	Target category	Computational Requirement
Different categories, same codes	Jewish and Lutheran (Code 9)	Match	Different	Match	Different	Align categories, then recode codes
Same categories, different codes	Uniting Church/Methodist (Code 3 and Code 5)	Different	Match	Different	Match	Align categories, assign codes, then recode codes
Different categories, different codes	Judaism (Code 12) and Jewish (Code 9)	Different	Different	Different	Different	Align categories, then recode codes
Same categories/codes, different encoding	ISLAM (Code 8) Islamic (Code 10)	Same	Same	Same	Same	Address source of computational difference (e.g. spelling)

It is important to recognise the complications resulting from differential encoding of content in the variables. For example, the use of three separate terms - “OTHER”, “Other (please specify)” and “Other religions - Please specify” all reflect the same underlying concept, but result in different outcomes when compared algorithmically due to differential encoding of the content. Possible approaches to the treatment of such content is included in Section 4.

3.4.1 Sentinel and missing values

Along with the substantive content of variables, there is also a need for understanding the treatment of missing and sentinel values. The SDMX community define sentinel values as “a value that has a special meaning within the representation of its Component”, i.e. categories and codes in a code list that reflect outcomes that are indeterminate or outside the range of substantive categories relevant to the variable (such as a “Don’t know” response). A brief review of the automated harmonisations in the ADA and Sikt collections has shown that differences in the codes and categories assigned to these sentinel values are often the source of differential mappings between source and target variables, even where the codes and categories associated with substantive elements in the variable are the same. An illustration of this is presented in Figure 13, where there are six different sentinel codes and eight different categories for a numeric count of the number of employees of the respondent.

Statistics Code Comparison Correspondence Tree					
Australian Survey of Social Attitudes					
	Australian Survey of Social Attitudes 2003	Australian Survey of Social Attitudes 2005	Australian Survey of Social Attitudes 2007	Australian Survey of Social Attitudes 2009	Australian Survey of Social Attitudes 2011
Item Name	aussa_2003_data	aussa_2005_data	aussa_2007_data	aussa_2009_data	aussa_2011_data
	V305	V396	V577	v367	h10
Don't know					-7
NOT APPLICABLE				-6	
Illegible or impossible value					-6
Multiple responses					-5
No partner					-4
SKIP				-2	
Skipped					-2
MISSING				-1	-1

Figure 13. Sample of sentinel value codes from AuSSA numeric variable.

The additional complication of these “special values” is that they are often managed differently within different software packages. The treatment of missing data in particular requires encoding in such a way as to enable the analysis of the values in multiple packages - an issue considered further below.

3.4.2 Transformation of source values to target values

The different variations in code and category combinations identified above highlight the complexities involved in the automation of the harmonisation process. As such, the representation of source-to-target mappings has generally been generated manually, often through the use of mapping spreadsheets. Packages such as `retroharmonize` have implemented mechanisms for generating and using such mappings⁴⁰ but still require manual input to specify the source and target code and category in the mapping.

Once these mappings have been identified, the transformation of underlying variable metadata and data is straightforward in most statistical languages. Similar to variable mapping, the transformation essentially involves the encoding of the source and target codes, and then a simple transformation of the source value to the target. A sample of code to achieve this, from the `retroharmonize` package, is presented in Figure 14.

```
## Transform values from source to target

ct %>% # Transform codes
  mutate ( val_numeric_target = case_when (
    val_numeric_orig == 1 ~ .data$val_numeric_orig,
    val_numeric_orig == 2 ~ 0,
    TRUE ~ 99999
  )) %>% # Transform category labels
  mutate ( val_label_target = case_when (
    val_numeric_orig == 1 ~ "trust",
    val_numeric_orig == 2 ~ "distrust",
    TRUE ~ "declined"
  )) %>% # Return a table of transform
  distinct ( across(all_of(c("filename",
                             "val_numeric_orig", "val_numeric_target",
                             "val_label_orig", "val_label_target")))
            )
)
```

Figure 14. Harmonisation of codes and categories in `retroharmonize`.

⁴⁰ <https://retroharmonize.dataobservatory.eu/articles/crosswalk.html>

More complex harmonisation processes can involve mapping, combination and/or transformation of several source values (such as questions associated with education history or occupation), or transformation of response scales of different lengths into a common scale. The increasing complexity of a harmonisation workflow often requires increasing levels of human judgement. It is for this reason that for this discussion we have focussed primarily on the mapping of single variables in the first instance.

3.4.3 Encoding of mappings

To enable reusability of variable and value mappings, and potentially reduce the need for completing future mappings, it would also be beneficial to represent the mappings in an interoperable format. Both the DDI and SDMX standards have means for encoding such mappings: the `ClassificationCorrespondenceTable` in DDI⁴¹ and the `StructureMap` in SDMX.

For the purposes of cross-domain interoperability, however, it may be of benefit to look at more general correspondence mapping approaches. One such approach in the ontology management domain is the Simple Standard for Sharing Ontological Mappings (SSSOM)⁴². Based on the content of the DDI variable cascade, and the available properties in the SSSOM, it should be possible to represent specific code and category mappings as an SSSOM `Mapping`, and to combine the output of the full range of codes mapped within a target variable as an SSSOM `MappingSet`, which could then be represented in an SSSOM `MappingRegistry`. The TSV serialisation of the SSSOM also appears to be well-aligned with the long-format representation of the retroharmonize crosswalk.

3.5 Data type harmonisation

A final set of harmonisation activities required in data harmonisation is data type harmonisation. This is primarily oriented towards the formatting and encoding of variables, and their representation and storage in specific statistical packages.

It is possible to specify the format of such content in a harmonisation process, but this is often not done in advance, and can lead to similar mismatches to those occurring for code and category processing. Two attributes of interest here are the specification of variable types (nominal, ordinal, integer or ratio) and the specification of data types (integer, character, etc.). For a single dataset these specifications are generally non-problematic, but where there are type mismatches between two source datasets, these will regularly result in errors in any machine processing that occurs.

A second challenge in the mismatch of formats is in the mechanism used for storing and representing missing and sentinel values. Datasets exporting from different software packages store and treat these values in different ways depending on the usage. For example, SPSS allows

⁴¹ <https://ddialliance.github.io/ddimodel-web/DDI-L-3.3/item-types/ClassificationCorrespondenceTable/>

⁴² <https://mapping-commons.github.io/sssom/>

specification of missing values in two forms (user-missing and system-missing) and using any numeric character, while R uses the indicator 'NA' as a representation of missingness. Packages also vary to the extent that they will allow users to specify a given value as missing. As seen in Section 3.4.1, inconsistency in these practices across datasets results in further mismatches in variables that may result from either code differences or the encoding of data within data files. For this reason, harmonisation of variable data types forms the last stage of the data harmonisation process. This then requires two potential processes - often in combination):

- Import of variable metadata that is available with the data (either in an internal format such as SPSS or R);
- Transformation of the imported data into a consistent harmonised format.

In the DDI variable cascade, this form of standardisation can be achieved through the use of variable representations⁴³ which are integrated into the Represented Variable level of the variable cascade⁴⁴. For social science data, along with the Code List, the specification of a Representation associated with a RepresentedVariable can provide target formats, as well as the target codes and categories. Available attributes in DDI-Lifecycle can include:

- `RecommendedDataType`: either a term or reference to an established controlled vocabulary list. (Documentation recommends that the user should select from the W3C XML Schema Part 2 list of data types⁴⁵);
- `GenericOutputFormat`: specification for the preferred output format expressed in a generic way;
- `@missingValue`: an array of values that should be treated as missing values;
- `@blankIsMissingValue`: Boolean attribute indicating that a blank (no content) should be treated as a missing value;
- `@classificationLevel`: specifying the classification of the content as: Nominal, Ordinal, Interval, Ratio, or Continuous⁴⁶.

As a standard practice, it would therefore be optimal to specify each of these attributes, as well as the specified CodeList (representing Codes and Categories) in a Representation within a DDI RepresentedVariable, available through a Variable Registry. This then would be available to data processors as a target variable, and ideally prior to data collection as a Representation of a preferred ResponseType in a question. The DDI-Lifecycle Technical Specification provides an overview of how this could be implemented (Figure 15).

⁴³ <https://ddi-lifecycle-documentation.readthedocs.io/en/latest/TechnicalGuide/Representations.html>

⁴⁴ A Representation also includes the variable CodeList, specifying the specific set of Codes that are associated with the Categories identified in the Conceptual Variable.

⁴⁵ <http://www.w3.org/TR/2001/REC-xmlschema-2-20010502/#built-in-datatypes>

⁴⁶ This classification is derived from Stevens (1947).

Figure 15. Overview of Representation (inline) (Source: DDI Alliance Technical Guide, Figure 4).

With suitable implementation, data processors would then be able to access the representation within their given processing environment and correctly align the data formats in a similar process to the code and category harmonisation occurring earlier. The current development of the `retroharmonize` package provides an example of how this could be achieved, by capturing the source and destination formats in a variable crosswalk (Figure 16).

```
## Transform variable class from source to target

ct <- ct %>%
  mutate( class_target = ifelse(
    test = .data$var_name_target == 'rowid',
    yes = "character", # the rowid remains a character
    no = "numeric" # the variable is transformed to a numeric )
  )
```

Figure 16. Harmonisation of data formats (Source: Antal et al., 2022⁴⁷).

⁴⁷ <https://retroharmonize.dataobservatory.eu/reference/index.html#type-conversion>

3.5.1 Potential for cross-domain integration

The discussion above highlights the capacity for current social science infrastructure to support generic data formats, using the W3C DataTypes. Extending this further, it should also be possible to specify the use of standardised measures and formats. For example, there would be significant value in incorporating the representation of units of measure such as those under consideration in the CODATA Digital Representation of Units of Measure group⁴⁸. Standardised approaches to incorporating these into the Cross-Domain Interoperability Framework could be tested in Phase 3 of the Social Surveys work package.

3.5.2 Harmonising variable universes/populations

As discussed in Section 2.1 above, the surveys in our use case (ESS and AUSSI-ESS) were designed ex-ante to be representative of the same universe of people. It is often the case, however, in ex-post harmonisation that the universe of people being studied differs, partly because the data collection is not initially intended to be harmonised (i.e. in an ex-post design). Given the presence of this issue across multiple work packages (discussed in Section 2.1), this suggests that population harmonisation would be an area for development in future WorldFAIR activity. The development of a joint approach to harmonisation of (sub-)universes would be of significant benefit for applying the outcomes of this WP to other domains and to other cross-national or cross-temporal research designs, but such development is beyond the scope of this Deliverable.

3.6 Reproducibility and documentation

Strictly speaking, reproducibility and documentation are not a requirement of the harmonisation process. But without documentation, there is no clear means for the end-user to understand the relationship between the source and target content, nor the decisions that have been made in the harmonisation process. Similarly, if a harmonisation is not reproducible, then it is likely to be questioned as to how it was achieved. As such, authors such as Granda and Blasczyk (2016) and Kolczynska (2022) argue that documentation and reproducibility are key outputs of any harmonisation process.

Recommended practices for these outputs are limited. Granda and Blasczyk probably provide the most comprehensive approach for this (see Figure 17). Critical in this context are transparent access to the harmonisation procedures used, descriptions of the decision-making that has led to the final outputs, and capacity to reproduce (and adjust) the final outputs.

⁴⁸ <https://codata.org/initiatives/task-groups/drum/>

- 5.1 Define the elements of the harmonization process and start documenting it from the beginning in order to ensure that all decisions are captured even before a definite plan to produce a public-use data file exists.
- 5.2 To the greatest extent possible, document each target variable with information from all source variables, transformation algorithms, and any deviations from the intended harmonized approach.
- 5.3 If possible, provide users with access to the original data files used in producing the harmonized file. If direct access to original data is not permissible due to confidentiality concerns, implement procedures to assist users in proper check-backs or re-transformations. Also consider implementing some form of restricted-use data agreement to access under controlled conditions.
- 5.4 Prioritize providing users with the code or syntax used in creating new variables for the harmonized file.
- 5.5 Provide users with as-complete-as-possible documentation, including crosswalks, which describe all the relationships between variables in individual data files with their counterparts in the harmonized file. An interactive, Web-based documentation tool is often the best way to present such documentation. Include original questionnaires and information about the data collection process whenever possible.
- 5.6 Report on as many of the elements of the data lifecycle as it applies to the particular harmonization process

Figure 17. Data and documentation for harmonised datasets (Source: Granda and Blasczyk, 2016).

There are no clear standards for the complete documentation of the harmonisation process. There are, however, possible approaches that could be adopted that may go some way to achieve this. Table 5, below, provides some candidate options for this. In terms of reproducibility, given the dependency on scripted approaches to the harmonisation process, adoption of code sharing practices such as those recommended by the FAIR for Research Software⁴⁹ working group would be a potential approach.

The other reproducible output of interest is likely the mappings of source to target content - at the variable, code, category and format levels. As proposed above, much of the content of interest would be accessible through variable and other registries, and would be referenceable from the data processing scripts. Here, a standardised means for connecting the inputs, mappings and outputs, likely one or more of the current mapping standards, would be clearly possible.

⁴⁹ See <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41597-022-01710-x>; and <https://rd-alliance.org/group/fair-research-software-fair4rs-wg/outcomes/fair-principles-research-software-fair4rs-0>

Table 5. Documentation options for data harmonisation.

Content for dissemination	Standard	Coverage
Inputs	DDI Lifecycle, DDI-CDI	Variable cascade
Mapping	DDI, SDMX, SSSOM	Variable code and category mapping
Process	FAIR for Research Software PROV SDTL	Processing code Specification of transformation process Abstraction of transformation process
Outputs	DDI Lifecycle, DDI-CDI	Variable outputs, study information
Documentation		Protocols, written text, etc.

4. Source data preparation

Many of the challenges in the integration of social science data result from the inconsistencies that exist in specific machine implementations of well-established human practice standards. While there is still a significant need for human input in the harmonisation process around issues of conceptual or methodological consistency, some of the machine interoperability challenges identified in Section 3 could be greatly improved through the application of more consistency in the processing of source data, i.e. the application of common processing rules for data prior to any efforts to integrate. For example, the proliferation of code-category mismatches identified in Section 3.4 is partly a function of the use of different patterns of capitalisation, punctuation and text encoding - mismatches that could be reduced by more standardised processing rules.

To this end, we see two broad areas for pre-processing of data that would assist in this process. These areas, consistent with the data harmonisation process covered in Section 3, include content pre-processing (of codes, categories and label text) and format processing (of numeric and character formats, and software specific encoding such as missing values). A preliminary list of pre-processing rules to address such errors has been drafted⁵⁰ and will be tested in Phase 3 of the work package.

There is a broader question of what might be considered “concept processing” of some of the content in these collections. Section 3.3 discussed the challenges of mapping variables to a target. Such mapping inherently requires the comparison of the conceptual meaning of a possible source variable with the target variable of interest, to determine if they are conceptually similar. At this point in time, such comparison is primarily manual. While there may be potential for using semantic similarity models to streamline this activity, one challenge comes from the need to look at the semantics across the combination of the different elements that make up a variable - the label, the categories (and their labels) and the code list used. Here some use of tagging or annotation of variable conceptual content may be of benefit as another pre-processing activity⁵¹.

⁵⁰ <https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/12hoRDUeA8tiVNjA4HDZOpN3MRz3RTGvpWsrvsXK8cE/edit?usp=sharing>

⁵¹ However this is out of scope for the work package at this time.

5. Next steps

This report has articulated a core workflow and a set of recommended practices for the conduct of harmonisation activities for social surveys. It considers the core steps involved in the harmonisation process, key issues that occur in the processing of data during this process, and potential resolutions of these issues. These resolutions are all oriented towards improving FAIR practices in the harmonisation process - through use of reusable, accessible metadata structures that can both improve processing consistency for current projects, and be applied to future harmonisation projects.

The third and final phase of this Work Package will focus on testing this workflow on new waves of data coming from the AUSSI and ESS projects. In Phase 3 we will seek to implement these proposed workflows and test and evaluate their suitability across the two partner organisations. This will particularly allow us to address Recommendations 6.3, 6.4 and 6.6 of the previous Deliverable 6.1 - establishing common, shared content (such as mappings, variables and scripts/code), embedding these with relevant content registries, and then evaluating their use in processing of new data.

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